

Towards a Defense-in-Depth Approach for Securing Collaborative Cloud Infrastructures

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Abstract—Data is wealth and this is indisputable. The one that owns the data may perform data analytics, understand the domain and the existing problems, propose solutions, even generate innovation. This is the reason why data ownership is so important and data owners have been reluctant in sharing their data. However, the last decade cloud infrastructure solutions enable collaborative data processing are increasingly adopted in research and industry, allowing data owners to make their datasets available for computation without directly exposing them, thus preserving confidentiality and acknowledging ownership, while harnessing the power of collaborative analytics and comparative analysis. Obviously, this paradigm introduces new challenges: protecting sensitive data from potentially malicious code, ensuring code execution integrity, and securing the underlying infrastructure. Existing approaches only partially address these issues. Some approaches focus on protecting the execution environment, others rely on pre-attested code—limiting exploratory research—and some adopt confidential computing techniques that shield data but assume both code and data are inherently trustworthy. In this work, we examine a more open and collaborative cloud infrastructure that executes unattested code directly on private data without requiring pre-approval. To address the resulting security and privacy challenges, we propose a Defense-in-Depth architecture that integrates static code analysis, dynamic behavioral monitoring, and container-based sandboxing. Our architecture secures the execution environment, preserves data confidentiality, and ensures computational integrity—even in multi-tenant settings where neither code or data can be trusted. This work lays the foundation for secure, privacy-preserving, and flexible collaborative cloud systems.

Index Terms—Collaborative Cloud, Defense-in-Depth, Privacy, Security, Trust

I. INTRODUCTION

Among collaborative cloud platforms, a growing subset enables unattested code execution—allowing users to remotely run custom scripts and programs on hosted infrastructure. Platforms like Google Colab [1] and Amazon SageMaker [2] offer such capabilities, empowering researchers and developers to offload computationally intensive tasks. While

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these platforms protect the infrastructure using sandboxing or virtualization techniques [3], their security model is designed around single-party trust: they assume that the code and data are provided by the same trusted user. As a result, they do not aim to protect data from potentially malicious code, or to ensure the correctness or integrity of computations across untrusted participants. To address such issues, several platforms like Azure Confidential Computing [4], PySyft [5], and Ocean Protocol’s Compute-to-Data [6] introduce privacy-preserving computation by separating data owners from code providers. These platforms rely on confidential computing principles to isolate data during processing and protect the execution environment. However, they usually allow only pre-approved software to execute on sensitive data [7], limiting the range of possible data-driven operations, ultimately hindering exploratory research and experimentation. Furthermore, they provide no visibility into the software’s behavior at runtime, assuming instead that statically attested code will behave securely. This assumption may not always hold true: vulnerabilities such as race conditions or runtime logic errors can still lead to data leaks or system instability. Moreover, malicious behavior—such as logic bombs or conditional exfiltration triggered at runtime—can evade static attestation. Furthermore, many applications are confidential or proprietary, making third-party audits infeasible [8]. In contrast, RAISE [9] supports a more flexible and open model: unattested code can be submitted by users and executed on private datasets, without exposing raw data to the code providers. However, this approach raises a critical security question: *How can we secure such a complex collaborative environment that enables unattested code execution on private, sensitive data, where both the code and the data can not be trusted?*

In this short, work-in-progress paper, we lay the foundations for a collaborative cloud architecture that ensures (a) the protection and integrity of the execution environment, (b) the privacy of the data, and (c) the integrity of the code execution. We achieve this by designing a Defense-in-Depth (DiD) architecture that combines lightweight software sandboxing with static code analysis and dynamic, behavioral monitoring during execution. To the best of our knowledge, this is the

first solution to introduce a comprehensive Defense-in-Depth architecture specifically tailored to secure privacy-preserving, cloud-based collaborative environments that support unattested code execution, where both the code and the data can not be trusted.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Existing works that address privacy and integrity in collaborative cloud environments typically fall into three categories: confidential computing, virtualization-based isolation, and behavioral monitoring.

Confidential computing approaches, such as those using Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs), isolate sensitive data within hardware-protected enclaves to prevent infrastructure-level access [10]. While recent extensions support data sharing across enclaves [11], these systems remain hardware-bound and incur high initialization costs, making them unsuitable for scalable, on-demand cloud deployments [12]. Software-based alternatives, such as Multi-Party Computation frameworks, avoid hardware dependencies and protect data privacy across non-colluding providers [13], but assume trusted code and lack defenses against unsafe or malicious software inputs.

To protect the execution environment, tools like Kata Containers, Firecracker, and gVisor isolate untrusted workloads through virtualization or syscall-level sandboxing [14]–[16]. These methods offer strong host protection but provide limited safeguards against runtime data misuse or attacks arising from adversarial inputs.

Behavioral monitoring techniques add a dynamic layer of defense. Taint-based models track data flows to block unauthorized propagation [17], while newer approaches employ Transformer-based models to detect anomalous process behavior based on system-level signals [18]. Hybrid systems have begun combining sandboxing with runtime monitoring into DiD architectures [19], but often omit static analysis, leaving critical blind spots.

In contrast, our work assumes mutual distrust between code, data, and infrastructure, treating the execution environment as an exposed attack surface. We propose a hardware-agnostic, multi-layer DiD architecture that unifies static analysis, dynamic monitoring, and sandboxing to ensure secure, privacy-preserving code execution in multi-tenant cloud settings.

III. SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

The RAISE platform is a public cloud infrastructure that enables secure, collaborative computations. Users upload both datasets and code to run experiments, where software is executed against data. To protect sensitive information, code providers never access the original datasets; instead, they receive synthetic data with matching structure for local development. During execution, only the code interacts with the real data, within a controlled environment with internet access, hosted in the infrastructure. Results are returned after execution. The execution environment is multi-tenant, meaning concurrent user jobs may share the same physical host. Our

work focuses on securing this environment. Accordingly, we define three core non-functional requirements (NFR):

- **NFR1:** The system must be able to protect and ensure the integrity of the execution environment.
- **NFR2:** The system must be able to preserve the privacy of user data during the experiment phase.
- **NFR3:** The system must be able to guarantee the integrity of the executed code.

IV. TRUST & THREAT MODEL

Our trust model comprises three distinct parties:

- **Data Owners (DOs):** Provide sensitive datasets and expect their data to remain confidential throughout the execution process. They do not trust Code Providers, whose code may attempt to leak or misuse data, and they rely on the Execution Environment (EE) to enforce strict data protection.
- **Code Providers (CPs):** Upload software for processing data and expect the code to run without interference or manipulation. They do not trust Data Owners, whose datasets may be adversarial or exploit vulnerabilities in the code, and depend on the EE to provide a fair and secure execution context.
- **Execution Environment (EE):** Executes code on private data and is assumed to be trusted by both DOs and CPs. However, it does not trust either party, as code may contain malware or sandbox escapes, and data may include malicious payloads. Therefore, it must be hardened as a potential attack surface.

The proposed threat model includes potential attacks during the code execution phase. Overall, three vectors of attacks are identified and some of the potential exploits are presented next.

A. Attacks against the execution environment

The execution environment is the primary attack surface, targeted by adversaries seeking to break isolation, disrupt co-resident workloads, or launch anonymous attacks using cloud resources. Threats include privilege escalation, logic bombs, obfuscated malware, and backdoors—delivered through unverified code, or crafted datasets designed to exploit software vulnerabilities during execution. As the platform allows unattested code and data, both known and zero-day exploits are considered plausible. Robust isolation and runtime detection are essential to identify and contain such threats, while ensuring accountability in the event of compromise.

B. Attacks against the data

Since original datasets are accessed during runtime, malicious code may attempt to exfiltrate them. Direct leaks may occur via web protocols (HTTP, sockets), while indirect methods may hide sensitive data in output files, logs, or metadata. These covert channels can bypass detection unless strict data flow and output inspection mechanisms are in place.

C. Attacks against the data processing software

These include direct attacks, such as adversarial inputs that manipulate output or poison models, and indirect attacks that exploit code vulnerabilities to escalate privileges or hijack sessions. For example, a data set may exploit deserialization flaws such as CVE-2020-14343 in unpatched PyYAML libraries, enabling arbitrary code execution. Such attacks underscore the need for pre-execution vulnerability assessment and runtime safeguards.

V. DEFENSE-IN-DEPTH ARCHITECTURE

To fortify the infrastructure and meet the proposed requirements, we introduce a Defense-in-Depth architecture that integrates static analysis, dynamic monitoring, and sandboxing. This layered approach is essential because no single mechanism can simultaneously safeguard data confidentiality, execution integrity and environment security. Often relying on a single defense makes the system vulnerable to a single point of failure [3]; if it is bypassed, the system is compromised. In contrast, combining multiple layers increases resilience: if one is evaded, others can still detect or mitigate the threat. Moreover, as modern malware is designed to evade static or dynamic techniques, layering both improves detection and narrows the attack surface.

Static analysis is performed immediately after code upload and before execution, enabling early detection of threats and preventing potential damage or data leaks. By halting the pipeline when issues are found, it also conserves computational resources that would otherwise be spent on dynamic analysis. Attacks targeting the code typically exploit vulnerabilities either in the code itself or its dependencies. To address this, the first step involves scanning the code and its dependencies for known vulnerabilities. By blocking the use of vulnerable software components, the infrastructure mitigates attacks that exploit such weaknesses. In addition, the system assesses the maliciousness of both the code and its dependencies by identifying known malicious libraries and inspecting code patterns that violate the platform’s policies or signal harmful intent. For instance, patterns indicative of malware—such as attempts to encrypt local files, escalate privileges, or generate excessive network traffic for a denial-of-service (DoS) attack—can be detected early. Static taint analysis is also applied to evaluate how the code intends to use the provided data and whether it might leak sensitive information to external or covert channels. This can be implemented using pattern matching, and static taint analysis software, like Semgrep [20] and CodeQL [21]. Enhanced by custom rules, these tools can be adapted to fulfill the specific requirements of each use case.

After passing static analysis, the code is matched with the associated dataset and deployed into the dynamic analysis environment. This environment is designed to closely replicate the production execution context and includes all necessary dynamic analysis tools. The rationale behind this design is that the more accurately the environment mimics production, the more reliably malware will exhibit its intended behavior.

This similarity serves to counteract obfuscation and evasion techniques, which often rely on environmental cues to detect whether the code is being analyzed. By minimizing the observable differences between analysis and production, it becomes significantly harder for malware to distinguish between the two and alter its behavior accordingly.

Dynamic analysis runs in isolated sandboxes, following the same multi-tenant model as production. The sandbox serves as a critical security layer, isolating untrusted code both from the host system and from other co-tenant executions. This isolation is essential, as even with advanced detection measures in place, an undetected threat could still cause damage if not properly confined. Additionally, sandboxes enforce strict resource constraints, limiting the memory, CPU, and network access granted to each analysis. This mitigates resource exhaustion attacks impacting the host or tenants. In order to ensure that the execution environment remains scalable, efficient, and hardware-agnostic, container-based isolation is employed. Specifically, the combination of gVisor and Docker preserves the lightweight nature, rapid startup, and scalability of containers while enhancing host isolation through gVisor’s user-space kernel protection mechanisms [22].

Finally, the dynamic analysis process comprises two key components. The first is a real-time malware detection mechanism that monitors behavioral characteristics—such as resource usage and process activity—to identify potentially malicious behavior. Powered by Transformers, this recent approach has shown promising results in detecting both known and zero-day threats [18]. The second component is dynamic taint analysis, which labels sensitive data and then tracks their flow through memory, processes, and system-level operations, such as file writes or network transmissions, during execution. This technique helps identify unauthorized data leaks or misuse by detecting instances where tainted data reaches unauthorized or covert channels [17], [23]. It is important to note that, during dynamic analysis, synthetic data are served to the code instead of real user data. This precaution prevents the leakage of actual sensitive information while still enabling the detection of malicious behavior, as leakage attempts are visible through interactions with the synthetic data. Overall, detection of harmful or unauthorized behavior reinforces accountability and supports the non-repudiation principle, while also acting as a deterrent by increasing the likelihood that malicious actions will be traced back to their origin.

The aforementioned defenses are integrated into a DiD pipeline, collectively designed to fulfill the NFRs of the cloud infrastructure’s execution environment. First, vulnerability assessment strengthens the code against exploitation via maliciously crafted inputs, thereby ensuring that the code operates as intended and maintaining its integrity (*NFR3*). It also protects the execution environment from vulnerability-based attacks, such as regular expression denial of service, insecure deserialization and arbitrary code execution (*NFR1*). Second, detecting malicious dependencies and code patterns helps defend the infrastructure against embedded threats. When combined with static taint analysis, this stage further

Fig. 1. Defense-in-Depth Architecture

mitigates the risk of data leakage through direct or covert channels, thus contributing to data privacy (*NFRI*, *NFR2*). However, because static analysis alone cannot fully capture the runtime behavior of software—especially in the presence of obfuscation techniques—dynamic analysis serves as the next layer of defense. Here, real-time malware detection and dynamic taint tracking identify malicious behavior and prevent data leakages during execution, further safeguarding both the environment and user data (*NFRI*, *NFR2*). Together, these layers form a cohesive DiD architecture that collectively satisfies all three system requirements.

VI. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

In this short concept paper, we presented a Defense-in-Depth architecture for cloud infrastructures that support collaborative data processing through the execution of untested code. Our approach combines multiple layers of defense—namely static analysis, dynamic analysis, and sandboxing—into a practical framework aimed at ensuring infrastructure security, code integrity, and data privacy. We have already begun implementing this architecture and plan to test and validate it in a production environment using real-world malware and adversarial scenarios. Our vision is to enable secure, trusted, collaborative cloud infrastructures supporting diverse data processing through untested code—without imposing strict limitations. This, in turn, fosters a more open form of collaboration while still respecting the privacy and security requirements of modern cloud systems.

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